

LIGHT SCATTERING IN SOAP-SOLVENT SYSTEMS. PART I. SODIUM
STEARATE IN GLYCERINE AND IN ETHYLENEGLYCOL :
DEPOLARISATION AND INTENSITY MEASUREMENTS

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The measurements of depolarisation factors and intensity of light scattered at different directions from gel-forming systems of sodium stearate in glycerine and in ethyleneglycol have shown that the size and anisotropy of the particles decrease during cooling. The gels of higher concentrations contain larger number of particles of slightly larger size than those of lower ones. An attempt has been made to explain the results on the consideration of the behaviour of soap in polar solvents.

Several investigators have measured the depolarisation factors and intensity of the light scattered in different directions from gel-forming systems of soaps in organic solvents with a view to studying the nature of particles in the system and the mechanism of gelation. The present investigation deals with the measurements of the values of depolarisation factors and intensity of light scattered in different directions by gel-forming systems of sodium stearate in two polar solvents, glycerine and ethyleneglycol, during their cooling from a high temperature as these solvents are known to possess pronounced co-dissolving power for soap (Palit, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 3120).

EXPERIMENTA

Gel-forming Systems.—Gel-forming systems containing different amounts of sodium stearate in glycerine and in ethyleneglycol were prepared in pyrex glass test tubes of internal diameter 1.5" by the usual method (Prasad and Hattiangdi, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 21A, 1). The test tube was heated in an oil-bath maintained at 120° and when the contents of the test tube reached the temperature of the bath, it was transferred to the observation bath for depolarisation measurements.

Depolarisation Measurements.—The experimental arrangement and procedure adopted for the depolarisation measurements were the same as used by Sundaram (*ibid.*, 1954, 40A, 176). The depolarisation factors of the light scattered at 45° (forward), 67°, 90°, 112° and 135° to the direction of the incident beam were measured, taking all the necessary precautions to minimise errors involved in the measurements.

Light Intensity Measurements.—The experimental arrangement for the measurement of intensity was the same as the one used by Sundaram and Desai (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1954, 20, 597), except that the observation bath, which was maintained at 120°, contained Nujol, instead of distilled water. The test tube containing the gel-forming system at 120° was placed in the observation bath and the intensities of light scattered at different angles were measured at intervals of 10° till the system cooled down to room temperature. The cooling of the system was effected at an average rate of 1 for every two minutes.

Measurement of the Gelation Temperatures.—Flemming's method was used for the determination of temperature of gelation in the usual manner (Flemming, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, 41, 427; Deshpande and Buch, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 321).

The results obtained show that the variations in the depolarisation factors and the intensity of scattered light, at different temperatures, are of the same nature for different concentrations of the soap. Fig. 1 shows the curves obtained by plotting the depolarisation factors ρ_v and ρ_h , for the transversely scattered light, against temperature and Fig. 2 shows the curves obtained by plotting the values of the intensity of transversely scattered light and the values of the dissymmetry ratio (I_{45}/I_{135}) against temperature, for the system containing 3% soap (temperature of gelation = 32°).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

DISCUSSION

Depolarisation Measurements.—It can be seen from Fig. 1 that no changes take place in the values of ρ_v , ρ_h and ρ_u for the transversely scattered light during cooling until a temperature, a few degrees higher than the gelation temperature, is reached. The values of ρ_v , which are initially low, decrease on further cooling, and again become nearly constant at room temperature. This indicates that the particles are initially slightly anisotropic in nature and that the anisotropy decreases during gelation. There is a slight increase in the values of ρ_h during the last stages of gelation. According to Krishnan (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 1A, 717, 782) ρ_h depends on both size and anisotropy. Thus, it seems that simultaneous changes in the size and anisotropy of the particles are taking place during the cooling of the systems, and they are of such a magnitude that no large changes in the values of ρ_h are brought about.

The values of ρ_u , which are initially constant, decrease during the later stages of cooling and become constant at about room temperature. Sivarajan (*Curr. Sci.*, 1951,

20, 202) has stated that when the value of ρ_h is nearly unity, the values of ρ_u can be split up into the anisotropic part and the size part as follows: Contribution due to anisotropy = $2\rho_v/1 + \rho_v$; contribution due to size = $\Delta\rho_u = \rho_u - 2\rho_v/1 + \rho_v$.

At the other values of ρ_h , these relations give only approximate indications of the size and the anisotropy effects. The values of $\Delta\rho_u$ have been calculated at different stages of cooling and plotted against temperature (Fig. 1). It is found that the values of $\Delta\rho_u$ remain constant during the cooling of the systems until a temperature, a few degrees above the gelation temperature, is reached. Below this temperature the values decrease during gelation and become constant at room temperature. This shows that the size of the particles decreases during the cooling and consequent gelation of these systems.

The relations put forward by Ganesan (*Phys. Rev.*, 1924, 23, 63) and Guinand and Tounelat (*Compt. rend.*, 1947, 228, 1029) connecting the depolarisation value with the angle of scattering, are not found to be applicable to the systems studied.

Intensity Measurements.—It can be seen from Fig. 2 that the intensity of light scattered by the systems remains constant up to about 60° and then increases continuously during the setting of the systems to gels. This indicates that the particles in these systems increase in number and/or size during gelation. The measurements of the depolarisation factors have, however, shown that the size and anisotropy of the particles decrease during gelation. Hence, it can be concluded that the observed increase in the values of intensity is probably due to an increase in the number of scattering particles.

Angular Variation of Intensity.—From theoretical considerations Mie (*Ann. Physik*, 1908, 25, 377), Shoulejkin (*Phil. Mag.*, 1908, 48, 307), Blumer (*Z. Physik*, 1925, 32, 112; 1926, 38, 304, 920) and Krishnan (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1934, 1A, 147) have shown that with large particles the intensity of the light scattered in the forward direction is greater than that in the backward direction. Their results lead to the conclusion that an increase in the ratio I_{45}/I_{135} indicates an increase in the size of the particles. The values of this ratio at various stages of cooling of the systems studied in this investigation have been plotted against temperature (Fig. 2). These values remain constant up to a certain temperature, beyond which they decrease during the cooling and gelation of the systems, indicating thereby that the size of particles is comparatively large in the initial stages and decreases during cooling and gelation. This conclusion supports the deductions made from the values of ρ_h and $\Delta\rho_u$.

Oster ("Progress in Biophysics and Biophysical Chemistry" Butterworth Springer Ltd., London, 1950, Vol. I, p. 80) has shown that in a system containing very large independent particles, the values of the ratio I_{45}/I_{135} increase with increase in particle size and approach the maximum value of 2.44 in the case of rod-like particles, and 5.98 in the case of disc-like particles, whereas for spherical particles, this ratio increases very rapidly with increase in the size of the particles. In the present investigation the maximum values found for the ratio lie between 3 and 3.4, indicating that the particles in these systems are likely to be in the form of coils or rods.

Effect of Concentration on Intensity.—It is observed that the increase in the concentration of the gel-forming substance in both systems causes an increase in the intensity

of the scattered light as well as in the dissymmetry ratio. However, the increase in the intensity and the dissymmetry ratio is not as large as the increase in the amount of the disperse phase in the gel-forming solution owing to the increase in the concentration. Hence, it is probable that gels of higher concentrations contain a larger number of particles of a slightly larger size than gels of lower concentrations.

From the above study, the following conclusions have been drawn regarding the changes in shape and size of particles in the two systems :

- (i) The size of the particles decreases during cooling and gelation.
- (ii) The scattering particles increase in number.
- (iii) The particles at first join together to form coils.
- (iv) A gel of higher concentration contains larger number of particles of slightly larger size than a gel of lower concentration.

These conclusions suggest the following mechanism for formation of the gels studied. The soap on mixing with the solvent forms initially a dispersion which is molecular only to a small extent and consisting chiefly of independent colloidal micelles. On cooling the system, reduction in thermal agitation and the nature of the soap-solvent molecules give rise to the possibility of a combination of the two in two different ways, namely (1) the hydrocarbon tail of the soap attracts the hydrocarbon part of the alcohol as in the case of soap-water system, and (2) the polar part of the soap is oriented towards the solvent. Cooling also throws out some of the soap which may be in the molecular solution, thus increasing the number of particles. During the process of aggregation the particles change in shape as indicated by the changes in ρ_v values. The change is such that the particles decrease in size. The apparent contradiction of particles aggregating to give finally a particle of decreased size can be explained by the consideration that by size is meant the largest dimension occurring in the particle (length in the case of rods, diameter in the case of spheres, etc.) and not its volume. It would then be possible for the particles to form larger ones (with larger volume) and still their size may decrease owing to a change from the non-spherical (rod or coil) to a spherical shape, as the sphere has larger volume for the same dimension. This argument is supported by the fact that the final particles are more isotropic than the initial ones.

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